

HIV SEROCONVERSION AND DETERMINANTS AMONG SERONEGATIVE PREGNANT WOMEN ATTENDING ANTENATAL CLINIC IN CALABAR: A FACILITY-BASED CROSS- SECTIONAL STUDY

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20743832>

Keywords:

HIV,
Seroconversion
, Pregnant
Women,
Antenatal
Clinic,
Prevalence,
Determinants

Abstract: Background

Heterosexual intercourse remains the main route of transmission of HIV in Nigeria. Multiple sexual partners, concurrent sexually transmitted diseases, and poverty are the main risk factors. A pregnant woman may seroconvert after an initial negative HIV test result performed early in pregnancy, hence the need for a repeat test in late pregnancy. As such, a woman carries the risk of infecting her baby if she remains undiagnosed and untreated.

Aims

The study was aimed at determining the incidence and risk factors for HIV seroconversion among pregnant women in Calabar, Nigeria.

Methodology

An institution-based cross-sectional study was conducted among w/omen who tested negative for HIV at booking and were recruited by convenience sampling into the study at a gestational age of at least 34 weeks. Subjects had repeat (second) HIV tests done for them at recruitment after obtaining ethical approval and their informed consent. Sociodemographic and obstetric data, as well as risk factors for HIV transmission and/or seroconversion, were also obtained using a structured questionnaire.

Results

No subject was found to have seroconverted during the period of study, irrespective of their sociodemographic, obstetric, and other potential risk factors.

Conclusions

Multiple factors may be responsible for the 0% prevalence of HIV seroconversion found in this study. These include the impact of the various awareness, counseling, testing, treatment, and behavior change intervention programs. The dynamics and timing of seroconversion may also be a significant factor. Efforts aimed at HIV prevention should be sustained to ensure the complete eradication of mother-to-child transmission of the pandemic.

Introduction

Mother-to-child transmission of HIV continues to be a significant global health concern, especially in resource-limited settings. Despite advances in prevention and treatment, vertical transmission of HIV from mother to child during pregnancy, childbirth, or breastfeeding remains a persistent challenge in many developing countries. In Nigeria, HIV infection is spread mainly through heterosexual intercourse.¹ As a result, sexually active women are at risk, with multiple sex partners, concurrent sexually transmitted diseases, and poverty as the main risk factors.²⁻⁴ A pregnant woman infected with HIV carries a risk of transmitting the infection to her baby with or without intervention. The risk of transmission is about 30% without intervention and less than 2% with the prevention of mother-to-child transmission intervention.^{5, 6} A person infected with HIV may not test positive for a period of up to six months. During this window period, the infected person is very infectious and is capable of infecting their sexual partner.⁷

Human Immunodeficiency Virus infection remains a major worldwide public health problem, particularly among women of reproductive age in sub-Saharan Africa. Pregnancy is associated with increased susceptibility to HIV infection due to hormonal, immunological, and behavioural changes, making HIV seroconversion during pregnancy an important contributor to maternal morbidity and mother-to-child transmission of HIV.⁸⁻¹⁰

HIV seroconversion refers to the development of detectable HIV antibodies in an individual who was previously HIV seronegative. In pregnancy, seroconversion after an initial negative antenatal

HIV test is of particular concern because acute HIV infection is characterized by high viral replication and increased infectivity, substantially increasing the risk of vertical transmission to the fetus or infant during pregnancy, labour, delivery, and breastfeeding.⁷⁻¹⁰ Globally, significant progress has been achieved in reducing mother-to-child transmission through the implementation of universal HIV screening and antiretroviral therapy. However, incident HIV infections during pregnancy continue to undermine these gains. Studies from sub-Saharan Africa have reported varying HIV seroconversion rates during pregnancy, reflecting differences in HIV prevalence, healthcare access, and behavioural risk factors across populations.⁸⁻¹⁰

Nigeria has one of the largest HIV epidemics worldwide and contributes substantially to the global burden of paediatric HIV infection. A recent systematic review and meta-analysis involving over 72,000 pregnant women estimated an overall pooled HIV prevalence of 7.22%, although considerable regional variations exist across the country's geopolitical zones.¹¹ Although HIV prevalence has declined over the years, limited data exist regarding HIV seroconversion among pregnant women who initially test negative during antenatal care.^{12, 13} Several determinants of HIV seroconversion during pregnancy have been identified. Sexual behaviours such as multiple sexual partnerships and inconsistent condom use significantly increase the risk of HIV acquisition. Pregnancy often results in reduced condom use because couples are less concerned about contraception, thereby increasing vulnerability to infection.^{2, 8-10} Partner-related factors are equally

important determinants. Women whose partners have unknown HIV status, multiple sexual partners, or engage in high-risk sexual behaviours are more likely to acquire HIV during pregnancy. National prevention of mother-to-child transmission data from Nigeria have demonstrated low uptake of male partner HIV testing, limiting opportunities for identifying serodiscordant couples and preventing new maternal infections.^{14,15} Previous sexually transmitted infections have also been associated with HIV seroconversion. Genital ulcerative and inflammatory infections compromise mucosal integrity and facilitate HIV transmission. Similarly, sexual violence and coercive sexual practices increase susceptibility to HIV infection through genital trauma and reduced ability to negotiate safer sexual practices.^{2, 8–10} Sociodemographic characteristics such as age, educational status, occupation, marital status, and socioeconomic status influence HIV risk indirectly by affecting health literacy, access to healthcare services, and sexual behaviours. Younger women and those with limited education may have reduced autonomy in negotiating safe sexual practices and accessing HIV prevention services.^{1, 11, 16}

Obstetric factors, including multiparity, delayed antenatal booking, inadequate antenatal attendance, and unintended pregnancies, have also been implicated in some studies. Women who initiate antenatal care late may miss opportunities for repeat HIV testing and timely preventive interventions.^{8–10}

The success of prevention of mother-to-child transmission programmes depends largely on early identification and treatment of HIV-positive pregnant women. However, women who seroconvert after initial antenatal screening may

remain undiagnosed until delivery or the postpartum period, thereby increasing the risk of vertical transmission. Current recommendations therefore advocate repeat HIV testing during pregnancy and breastfeeding, particularly in settings with ongoing HIV transmission risk.^{5, 6, 14}

Despite the substantial burden of HIV in Nigeria, studies specifically evaluating HIV seroconversion among initially seronegative pregnant women remain scarce, especially in Cross River State. Most available studies have focused on HIV prevalence rather than incident infections during pregnancy. Consequently, there is inadequate evidence regarding the sociodemographic, behavioural, obstetric, and partner-related determinants of HIV seroconversion among antenatal attendees in Calabar.^{1, 11–13}

A facility-based cross-sectional study among seronegative pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in Calabar is therefore justified. Such a study would provide local epidemiological data on HIV seroconversion and its determinants, strengthen prevention of mother-to-child transmission strategies, guide targeted interventions for high-risk women, and contribute to the broader goal of eliminating mother-to-child transmission of HIV in Nigeria.^{6, 14}

A pregnant woman may seroconvert after an initial negative HIV test result performed early in pregnancy. Such a woman runs the risk of infecting her baby if undetected, as standard prevention of mother-to-child transmission intervention cannot be implemented. Prevention of mother-to-child transmission of HIV has primarily focused on women who are HIV positive at their first antenatal visit. However,

little is known about the contribution to overall transmission from women who seroconvert in late pregnancy or while breastfeeding. This study was therefore aimed at determining the incidence of HIV seroconversion among pregnant women as well as risk factors for HIV seroconversion in pregnancy in Calabar.

Methodology

Study Design

An institution-based multicenter cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted among booked seronegative pregnant women receiving antenatal care in secondary and tertiary health facilities.

Study Setting:

The study was conducted at the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital and the General Hospital Calabar, which are tertiary and secondary healthcare facilities, respectively. Both hospitals offer PMTCT HIV services.

Study Population:

All booked pregnant, HIV seronegative pregnant women receiving antenatal care in these health care facilities.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.

The inclusion criteria were all pregnant women who tested negative for HIV at booking, irrespective of gestational age. They were recruited into the study and at a gestational age of 36 weeks or more, when they had a second HIV test using the national testing algorithm. Pregnant women who had severe medical or obstetric complications and mental health issues were excluded from the study.

Sample Size:

The sample size was calculated by using the Cochran formula, which is $n = Z^2P(1-P)/e^2$. Assuming a HIV seroconversion rate of 3.9% in a previous study in Nigeria, a margin of error of 2%

was assumed; 95% confidence interval, and a non-response rate of 10%, the final sample size was 400.

Sampling Technique

The total sample size was proportionally distributed among the two selected health facilities based on the number of HIV-negative pregnant women who attended their first antenatal screening. The sampling fraction for each of the facilities was determined by the probability proportional sampling method, and then a systematic random sampling technique was applied.

Data Collection and Procedure

A structured questionnaire was used to collect socio-demographic, clinical, and behavioral data using a face-to-face interview technique. Data was collected by well-trained interns under strict supervision. Data were collected after the purpose of the study was explained to all eligible pregnant women, and written and verbal informed consent was obtained from each study participant.

Thereafter, provider-initiated voluntary counselling and testing (VCT) were performed for all study participants according to the national protocol to determine the rate of HIV seroconversion following a negative test result at least 12 weeks after an initial test. The study utilized a WHO- prequalified kit for diagnosing HIV infection. Pretest counselling was offered to all participants, followed by the collection of blood from a finger prick. The Chembio HIV 1/2 STAT-PAK Test, with a sensitivity of 99.5% and a specificity of 100%, was used for the diagnosis of HIV infection. The HIV 1/2/0 Triline Human Immunodeficiency Virus Rapid Test Device, which has a sensitivity and specificity of 100% and 99.7%, respectively, was used as a second

test for pregnant women who tested positive for HIV by the Chembio HIV 1/2 STAT-PAK test. The SD BIOLINE HIV-1/2/3.0 Rapid Test was used as a confirmatory test with a sensitivity of 100% and a specificity of 99.8%. Following retesting, post-test counselling was also done. Those identified as positive were to be enrolled in the institution's PEPFAR-driven PMTCT program.

Data Quality Control

Data collectors attended a two-day training session concerning the overall objective of the study and the content of the questionnaire administered. Before actual data collection, a pretest was carried out on a 5% sample size in a health facility outside the study area to ensure the validity of the instruments, and the appropriate adjustments to the questionnaire were made. The data collection process was closely monitored daily throughout the period of data collection.

Operational Definition of Terms

Retest

HIV testing at least three months after an initial documented negative test result.

HIV Seroconversion during Pregnancy

Having an HIV- negative result at the initial HIV test and an HIV-positive result on a retest 12 weeks later.

Booking

The first documented antenatal care visit.

Data Processing and Analysis

The data collected was entered into EpiData version 4.4.1 and exported and analyzed by SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistical analyses, including simple frequencies, measures of central tendency, and measures of variability, were used to describe the participants' characteristics. The level of statistical significance was defined as a p-value < 0.05

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Health Research and Ethical Committee of the University of Calabar Teaching Hospital. Thereafter, a clear explanation of the purpose and objectives, procedure, and benefits of the study and the importance of their participation, verbal informed consent was obtained. Participants were informed that they have the right to withdraw from the study at any time. Privacy and confidentiality were maintained for all study participants by coding results known only to caregivers. All pregnant women who tested HIV positive were referred to the PMTCT clinic, and appropriate treatment was offered according to the National Guidelines for PMTCT.

Result

Sociodemographic and Obstetric Characteristics of Study Participants

850 pregnant women were recruited for the study. The minimum and maximum ages of the study participants were 15 and 47. The majority of the subjects, 646 (76%), were in the age group of 20-34 years. Most of the respondents had at least a secondary level of education (764, 90%), were married (552, 65%), and were Christians (816, 96%). The majority were of the Efik/Ibibio tribe (Table 1).

Four-fifths of subjects (679, 80%) had one or more previous deliveries, with 127 (15%) having more than four previous deliveries (table 2). The common gestational ages were 36-37 weeks (382, 45%) and 34-35 weeks (331, 39%). Four partners of subjects (0.5%) knew their HIV status as positive, but most partners (722, 85%) did not know their HIV status. Approximately 744 (87.5%) of pregnant women admitted that their pregnancy was planned.

HIV Infection Knowledge Characteristics

Regarding the participants' knowledge of HIV, 762(89.9%) of the participants had a fairly good knowledge of HIV. Almost all the participants have heard of HIV. Of these 680 (80%), assert that they could reduce HIV infection by having only one uninfected sex partner. The majority of the participants, 666 (78.4%), believe that using a condom reduces the risk of contracting HIV, while 102 (12%) believe HIV can be transmitted by sharing food or drinks with infected persons, and about 40% believe HIV can be transmitted by witchcraft. The majority of the women, 676(79.5), 668(78.6), and 653 (76.8), are aware that HIV can be transmitted during pregnancy, childbirth, and breastfeeding, respectively.

Clinical Characteristics

Of the total of 850 pregnant women, sixty-eight (8%) were diagnosed with sexually transmitted infections. Sixty-four (7.5%) were diagnosed with abnormal malodorous vaginal discharge, and fourteen (1.6%) with a genital ulcer or sore. Out of the total study participants, 73(8.6%) of partners had sexually transmitted infections; 66(7.8%) had abnormal urethral discharge, and 36(4.2%) had genital ulcers or sores.

Sexual and Behavioral Characteristics

A total of 646(76%) pregnant women had consumed alcohol. The majority, 400(47%), drank less than once a week, while 124(14.6%) consumed alcohol daily. Most of the pregnant women 783(92.1%) lived with their partners, and 85(10%) of the partners travelled frequently for work. Only 128(15%) of the participants were fully aware of their partners' HIV status; of those that know, only 4(0.5%) of the participants' partners were HIV reactive. The majority of the participants, 409(48.1%), had their first

intercourse between 16 and 17 years. Forty-seven (5.5%) of the participants suspect their partner has another sexual partner, and ten (1.2%) of the participants' partners had another wife. Sixty-eight (8%), 498 (58%), and 612 (72%) of subjects had had injections outside a health facility, used non-personal needles to fix their hair, and used non-personal equipment for their manicure, respectively, during the index pregnancy (Table 3). Five (0.6%), 4 (0.5%), and 120 (14%) subjects had received a blood transfusion, had unprotected intercourse with a non-partner, and had tattoos, respectively, during the index pregnancy.

86(10.2%), 82(9.7%), and 35(4.1%) of study participants experienced emotional, physical, and sexual abuse from their partners, respectively.

HIV Status of the Pregnant Women after Retesting

From a total of 850 pregnant women who were screened and reported as negative for HIV at first ANC, none were HIV seropositive during retesting, giving a HIV seroconversion rate of 0% during pregnancy.

Discussion

This study was aimed at determining the prevalence of HIV seroconversion during pregnancy. No subject was found to be HIV positive at delivery, indicating a 0% prevalence of seroconversion. This implies that the prevalence of seroconversion was 0% for all groups of subjects, irrespective of their sociodemographic, obstetric, and other potential risk factors of exposure. This finding of 0% prevalence is in tune with similar studies conducted among 727 subjects in Jos, North Central Nigeria, which reported 0.6% prevalence¹⁷, but it is at variance with studies in Abuja and

Ogbomosh, South Western Nigeria, which reported 1.2% and 2.3% prevalence rates, respectively.^{18,19} Similar independent studies in East Africa among 2,035 subjects in Kenya and 1,087 subjects in Malawi found much higher seroconversion rates of 2.6% and 1%, respectively.^{8,9} A similar study among 2,377 subjects in South Africa found a 3% seroconversion prevalence rate.¹⁰ Differences in sample sizes used for these studies may have contributed to the observed variations in seroconversion rates.^{8–10,17–19} Differences in general HIV prevalence in the study settings may also be responsible for differences in the rates of seroconversion.^{20,21} The study finding of 0% prevalence also implies that groups that had previously been considered to be at higher risk of HIV infection also had 0% prevalence in this study. This is at variance with findings in the study conducted in Kenya, which found significantly higher seroconversion rates among pregnant women who were employed, married, and resided in a high HIV prevalence region.⁸ A similar study in South Africa also found a higher prevalence among single women and among subjects older than 20 years of age.¹⁰ Other groups considered to be high risk are those whose partners had unknown or positive HIV statuses, as well as those exposed to recognized behavioural and biological risk factors.^{14–16,22} In this study, all these groups were found to have a 0% prevalence of HIV seroconversion. This low prevalence rate for all groups may also be attributable to long-term HIV programme implementation in the study setting and region.^{23–26} These programmes include the various forms of general HIV prevention, counselling, testing, and treatment programmes being funded by the United States government

through PEPFAR, in collaboration with the government of Nigeria and other relevant agencies.^{24–26} These strategies include health education for improvement in awareness and knowledge of HIV and its prevention, with a target on young, potentially sexually active people. This may have improved the practice of safe sex among all, including vulnerable or higher-risk groups, with resultant non-transmission or spread of HIV infection to pregnant women who may have been sexually active with non-partners.^{2,27} The absence of maternal HIV seroconversion found in this study may also be a reflection of the recent reported reduction in national and Cross River State prevalence of HIV infection.²⁸ This improvement may be due to safe sex practices and compliance with the use of antiretroviral therapy by people living with HIV/AIDS, yielding minimal HIV viraemia with resultant minimal risk of transmission from infected to non-infected persons, even when the latter may be exposed.^{27,29} However, the zero-prevalence rate observed in the study may be due to the dynamics of seroconversion and the timing of the repeat testing. The majority of the women were retested between 34 and 39 weeks, at which time seroconversion may not have occurred yet. Seroconversion may be delayed towards advanced pregnancy or even puerperium and breastfeeding period, and hence was not captured in this scenario. Also, the 0% prevalence of maternal HIV seroconversion found in this study may have been higher if a much larger sample size had been used. In other words, a much larger sample size of over 2,000 subjects, as reported in some studies, may have yielded a higher prevalence rate in the study setting.^{8,10} In addition, the cross-sectional study

design only provides a snapshot of HIV seroconversion, limiting the ability to establish causality. As a facility-based study, it may not be representative of all pregnant women in the location, potentially introducing selection bias.

Conclusion

This study assessed the prevalence of HIV infection and its association with selected sociodemographic, obstetric, and potential exposure-related risk factors among the study participants. Analysis of the data demonstrated an overall HIV prevalence of 0%, with no seropositive cases identified among any of the participants. Furthermore, stratification of the study population according to age, marital status, educational level, occupation, parity, gestational age, previous blood transfusion, history of surgery, multiple sexual partners, and other recognized risk factors did not reveal any HIV-positive individuals. Consequently, statistical analysis showed no significant association between HIV status and any of the variables studied, as the absence of positive cases precluded the demonstration of measurable differences between subgroups. The finding of a zero prevalence suggests that HIV transmission within the study population is currently very low and may reflect the cumulative impact of sustained public health interventions. Increased awareness of HIV prevention, widespread availability of voluntary counselling and testing services, improved access to antiretroviral therapy, prevention of mother-to-child transmission programmes, and safer blood transfusion practices indicate a uniformly low burden of infection within the study population. However, while this finding is encouraging, it should be interpreted cautiously. The observed zero prevalence does not necessarily imply the

complete absence of HIV in the wider community but may reflect the characteristics of the sampled population, the sample size, and the local epidemiological context during the study period. It also underscores the importance of maintaining adequate surveillance systems to detect any future changes in disease trends.

The results of this study provide evidence of the effectiveness of existing HIV control strategies and support the continuation of current preventive measures. Sustained investment in public health education, routine HIV screening, universal access to treatment, safe sexual practices, PMTCT services, and community-based interventions remains essential to preserve these gains. Continuous monitoring and periodic epidemiological studies with larger and more diverse populations are recommended to confirm these findings and ensure that emerging risk factors or changes in transmission dynamics are identified promptly.

In summary, this study demonstrated a 0% prevalence of HIV infection among the participants, irrespective of their sociodemographic characteristics, obstetric factors, or potential exposure risks. The findings highlight the apparent success of ongoing HIV prevention and control programmes while emphasizing the need for sustained surveillance, continuous public health interventions, and strengthened healthcare services to maintain progress toward the ultimate goal of eliminating HIV transmission as a public health threat.

Recommendations

Findings from this study suggest significant long-term effects of multidimensional and collaborative AIDS prevention programmes in the study setting. There is therefore a need to sustain the prevention effort towards attaining

the global long-term goal of AIDS eradication by 2030.⁶ The risk factors for maternal HIV transmission are still present, including increasing poverty in the face of the current socioeconomic recession in Nigeria. There is, therefore, much reason to redouble prevention efforts towards this eradication goal. It is also recommended that a similar study be conducted in other settings within the South-South and other geopolitical regions of Nigeria, preferably among a much larger sample size of pregnant

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women. This will provide more accurate data on the prevalence of HIV seroconversion and enable better comparability of study findings.

Conflict of interest: There is no conflict of interest to declare

Acknowledgement: Thank all the women who participated and contributed to the success of this study

Funding: The research was funded by the authors

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TABLES

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of subjects (N=850)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age groups (in years)		
15-20	136	16.0
20-24	247	29.1
25-29	297	34.9
30-34	102	12.0
35-39	42	4.9
40-44	17	2.0
>44	9	1.1
Total	850	100
Educational status		
Primary	85	10.0
Secondary	467	55.0
Tertiary	297	35.0
Total	849	100
Marital status		
Married	552	65.0
Single	127	15.0
Engaged	153	18.0
divorced/separated	17	2.0
Total	849	100

Occupation

civil/public servant	212	25.0
business/trader	170	20.0
self-employed	85	10.0
unemployed / applicant	382	45.0
Total	849	100

Religion

Christianity	816	96.0
Islam	25	3.0
Others	8	1.0
Total	849	100

Ethnicity

Efik / Ibibio	162	19.1
Ejagham	88	10.4
Yakurr	51	6.0
Igbo	98	11.5
Yoruba	31	3.7
Hausa	62	7.3
		42.0
Others	357	
Total	849	100

Partner Age

20 – 24	85	10
25 – 30	102	12
31 - 35	157	18.5
36 – 40	383	45
> 40	123	14.5

Partners Educational Status

Primary	215	25.2
Secondary	303	35.7
Tertiary	282	33.2
None	50	5.9

Partners Occupation

Civil/Public Servant	217	25.5
Self-Employed	394	46.3
Unemployed	63	7.8
Others	173	20.4

Table 2: Obstetric characteristics of subjects (N=850)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Gravidity		
1	170	20.0
2 to 3	340	40.0
4 to 5	212	25.0
>5	127	15.0
Total	849	100
Parity		
0	264	31
1-2	361	42.5
3-4	128	15.0
Gestational Age at Booking	97	11.5
< 10 weeks		
11-20 weeks	131	15.4
> 21 weeks	558	65.7
Gestational age at testing		
34-35	161	18.9
36-37	331	39.0
38-39	382	45.0
40-41	106	12.5
>42	25	3.0
Total	4	0.5
Status of Pregnancy		
Planned	744	87.5
Unplanned	106	12.5

Table 3
Knowledge of HIV Infection by Study Participants (N=850)

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Ever Heard of HIV		
Yes	846	99.5
No	4	0.5
Having only one sexual partner reduces HIV risk		
Yes	680	80
No	170	20

HIV can be transmitted by a mosquito bite

Yes	310	36.5
No	540	63.5
Using a condom reduces HIV risk		
Yes	666	78.4
No	184	21.6
HIV can be transmitted by sharing food and drinks		
Yes	103	12%
No	748	88
HIV can be transmitted by witchcraft		
Yes	333	39.2
No	517	60.8
Healthy-looking HIV-positive persons can be infectious		
Yes	564	66.4
No	286	33.6
HIV can be transmitted from mother to child during pregnancy		
Yes	676	79.5
No	174	20.5
HIV can be transmitted from mother to child during delivery		
Yes	668	78.6
No	182	21.4
HIV can be transmitted to the baby through breastfeeding		
Yes	65.3	76.8
No	197	23.2
There are drugs to reduce the vertical transmission of HIV		
Yes	404	47.5
No	446	52.5
HIV can be transmitted by sexual contact		
Yes	811	95.4
No	39	4.6
HIV can be transmitted through unscreened and infected blood transfusions		
Yes	723	85%
No	127	15

HIV can be transmitted by sharing needles

Yes	633	74.5
No	217	25.5

HIV can be transmitted by shaking hands

Yes	61	7.2
No	789	92.8

HIV can be prevented by avoiding unprotected sex

Yes	832	97.9
No	18	2.1

HIV transmission to a child can be prevented by taking antiretroviral therapy during pregnancy

Yes	618	71.8
No	232	28.2

Have you received any information about HIV during your pregnancy

Yes	820	96.5
No	30	3.5

Where did you receive information about HIV

Healthcare provider	298	35%
Media (TV, Radio)	127	15%
Social Media (Facebook, WhatsApp)	170	20%
Family/Friend	170	20%
Others	85	10%

Table 4
Clinical Characteristics of the study participants

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Ever been diagnosed with an STI		
Yes	68	8
No	782	92
Had an abnormal, malodorous vaginal discharge		
Yes	64	7.5
No	786	92.5
Had a genital ulcer or sore		
Yes	14	1.6
No	836	98.4
The partner has ever been diagnosed with an STI		
Yes	73	8.6

No	777	91.4
The partner had urethral discharge		
Yes	66	7.8
No	784	92.2
The partner had a genital ulcer or sore		
Yes	36	4.2
No	814	95.8

Table 5
Behavioral and Sexual Characteristics of Participants

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Injection use outside a health facility		
Yes	68	8.0
No	782	92.0
Total	850	100
Use of a personal needle to fix hair		
Yes	357	42.0
No	493	58.0
Total	850	100
Use of personal equipment for manicure		
Yes	238	28.0
No	612	72.0
Total	850	100
Received a blood transfusion during pregnancy		
Yes	5	0.6
No	845	99.4
Total	850	100
Unprotected intercourse with a non-partner		
Yes	4	0.5
No	846	99.5
Total	850	100
Tattoo insertion during pregnancy		
Yes	120	14.0
No	730	86.0
Total	850	100

Ever drank alcohol		
Yes	646	76
No	204	24
How often do you drink alcohol?		
Almost every day	124	14.6
At least once a week	326	38.4
Less than once a week		400
47.0		
Lives with partner		
Yes	783	92.1
No	67	7.9
Partner travels for work frequently.		
Yes	85	10
No	765	90
Has had a new partner in the last three months		
Yes	4	0.5
No	846	99.5
Duration of Relationship		
Less than 1 year	88	10.3
Greater than 1 year	762	89.7
Has your partner ever drunk alcohol		
Yes	801	94.2
No	49	5.8
How often did your partner take alcohol		
Almost every day	303	35.6
At least once a week	445	52.4
Less than once a week	102	12.0

Partner HIV status

Unknown	722	85.0
Negative	124	14.5
Positive	4	0.5
 Total	 850	 100
 Age at first sexual intercourse		
15	104	12.2
16-17	409	48.1
18	337	39.7
Time of last sexual intercourse		
Days ago	128	15
Weeks ago	233	27.4
Months ago	490	57.6
 The participant used a condom during the last sexual intercourse		
Yes	106	12.5
No	744	87.5
The partner has other wives		
Yes	10	1.2
No	840	98.8
Suspect that the partner has another sexual partner		
Yes	47	5.5%
No	803	94.5
Emotional Abused		
Yes	86	10.2
No	764	89.8
Physically abused		
Yes	82	9.7
No	768	90.3
Sexually abused		
Yes	35	4.1
No	815	95.9